

Pattern of Tubulo-Interstitial Injury and its Association with Post-Induction Therapy Response in Proliferative Lupus Nephritis

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Keywords:

Tubulo-interstitial injury, proliferative lupus nephritis, post-induction therapy response, interstitial inflammation, acute tubular injury, interstitial fibrosis, tubular atrophy.

Abstract

Objective

The aim of the study was to assess the pattern of tubulo-interstitial injury and its association with post-induction therapy response in proliferative LN.

Methods

This multi-centered, prospective observational study was conducted from February 2020 – August 2021 (19 months). Class III and IV LN patients were included. With a total of 82 enrolled participants, we recorded the socio-demographic and histological characteristics and severity of injuries. Comparisons and associations between the therapy response and injuries were also evaluated.

Results

Interstitial Inflammation (84.1%) followed by Acute Tubular Injury (81.7%) were the most common types of tubulo-interstitial injuries. Furthermore, statistically significant association was found for all types of injuries, meaning, II ($p=0.001$); ATI ($p=0.025$) and interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy ($p=0.003$). Wire-loop lesion ($p=0.012$); global sclerosis ($p=0.001$) and fibrous crescent ($p=0.001$) were the types of glomerular lesions where statistically significant association was seen. Majority (64.5%) patients of mild II expressed complete response; 64.0% moderate category patients revealed deterioration; 51.6% patients of mild ATI showed complete response; 56.0% moderate and 24.0% severe interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy revealed deterioration. Statistically significant association was found in case of II ($p=0.001$) and IFTA (0.001).

Conclusion

Tubulo-interstitial injuries, particularly II and IFTA, showed significant associations with both histopathological severity and treatment outcomes in

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proliferative LN. These findings highlight their prognostic value in guiding therapeutic decisions.

Main points

- Interstitial inflammation (II) and acute tubular injury (ATI) were the most common tubulo-interstitial injuries, present in 84.1% and 81.7% of cases, respectively.
- A statistically significant association was observed between tubulo-interstitial injuries (II, ATI, IFTA) and LN class, particularly Class III and IV ($p < 0.05$).
- II and IFTA showed strong correlations with glomerular lesions such as global sclerosis, wire-loop lesions, and crescents ($p < 0.05$).
- Higher grades of IFTA were significantly associated with increased baseline and follow-up serum creatinine levels ($p < 0.01$), indicating prognostic relevance.
- Patients with mild II and IFTA were more likely to achieve complete response to induction therapy, while ATI did not show a statistically significant impact on treatment response ($p = 0.106$).

Introduction

The complicated autoimmune illness known as systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) includes renal involvement in the form of lupus nephritis (LN). It affects over 50% of SLE patients and is the most prominent and fatal consequence [1]. Autoantibodies form immune complexes that accumulate in the glomeruli, activating the complement system and attracting inflammatory cells, which leads to an inflammatory reaction. The definitive method for diagnosing LN is renal histopathological examination. According to the 2003 classification by the International Society of Nephrology and the Renal Pathology Society, LN is divided into six classes, ranging from Class I (minimal mesangial) to Class VI (advanced sclerosing LN) [2].

In LN, renal tubulointerstitial (TI) injury is frequent and is thought to be very useful for assessing the extent of renal damage, directing treatment and establishing prognosis [3]. While glomerular injury is believed to trigger proteinuria and hypoxia, these conditions can, in turn, lead to tubulointerstitial (TI) inflammation and fibrosis. Moreover, it remains uncertain whether TI damage occurs alongside LN or develops as a consequence of it. Both glomerular and TI injuries occur at the same time, but they arise through separate mechanisms [4]. Histological evidences of lupus-related TI injury indicates that local, in situ immune responses may play a role in initiating and sustaining TI inflammation and subsequent organ damage. In approximately half of patients, immune complexes are found deposited across the tubulointerstitial area, with distinctive accumulations seen in the tubular basement membranes [5].

The primary factor influencing these patients' total morbidity and mortality is LN [6]. Around 50% to 70% of patients attain remission with aggressive immunosuppressive (IS) regimens used to treat LN; the remaining 30% to 50% of patients may still develop end-stage renal disease (ESRD) after five years. As of now, the ISN/RPS categorization is widely utilized worldwide. Although LN may affect all kidney compartments, including the glomeruli, tubules,

interstitium, and vasculature, this classification is based solely on glomerular lesions [7].

Since the ISN/RPS categorization does not account for many additional lesions (podocytopathy, crescents, TI and vascular injuries), there are differing opinions regarding whether glomerular lesions can accurately predict renal response [8]. Moreover, there is a potential misconception that treatment response is uniform within each class, regardless of the specific histological lesions present. It is well established that TI injuries are independent risk factors in the progression of other glomerular diseases, such as IgA nephropathy. Similarly, in LN, TI injury independently predicts poor renal outcomes, including incomplete renal response, progression to CKD, and eventual development of ESRD. Therefore, TI damage warrants consideration for inclusion in the pathological classification system, highlighting the need to revise the current histological criteria for LN [9-11]. However, there is a dearth of information on the many forms of TI injuries in LN.

TI injury in LN is considered to be of great value for nephrologists for the evaluation of the degree of renal damage and to guide management and to determine prognosis. Furthermore, TI injury is a candidate for inclusion in the pathological classification of LN; however, data regarding the clinical and pathological factors co-related with different types of TI injury in LN are lacking. So, this study aims to determine the pattern of TI injury and its association with post-induction therapy response in proliferative LN.

Methods

This multi-centered prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Nephrology at Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH), National Institute of Kidney Disease and Urology (NIKDU), Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College Hospital (SShMCH) And Armed Forces Institute of pathology (AFIP), Dhaka Cantonment. Initially, 87 patients with biopsy confirmed proliferative LN were enrolled in the study; 5 patients were lost to follow-up; finally, 82 patients were included for final analysis in this study. So, 87 patients with Proliferative lupus nephritis were included in this study in between February 2020 –

August 2021 (19 months). Class III and IV LN patients with age ≥18 years of any gender were included. The exclusion criteria consisted of primary glomerulonephritis and other secondary glomerulopathies (diabetic nephropathy, infection related and ANCA associated glomerulonephritis etc.) and patients with LN who received immunosuppressive therapy before renal biopsy.

Before the commencement of the study, clearance from Research Review Committee (RRC) of nephrology and formal ethical approval was taken from the Ethical Review Committee (ERC) of DMCH. Later, due to declaration of DMCH as COVID-19 dedicated hospital, to have sufficient sample, approval to collect data from Department of Nephrology, NIKDU and SShMCH, was taken from respective authority. Patients with the clinical features of SLE with renal involvement were approached from the Department of Nephrology, DMCH, NIKDU and SShMCH. After written, informed consent from the patients was obtained, detailed history was taken and clinical examination was performed to identify presence of clinical criteria based on EULAR/ACR 2019 classification criteria for SLE. With all aseptic precautions, blood was drawn from peripheral veins, collected in vacuumed test tubes and sent to laboratory with proper identifications. Serum creatinine was measured using Erba Mannheim Creatinine kit and analyzed by Dimension EXL-200/Maglumi 2000 Analyzer.

Parameters of TI injuries:

Interstitial Inflammation: Inflammatory cells in the cortical area:

mild (1): <25%; moderate (2): 25%–50%; severe (3): >50% of cortical area.

Acute tubular injury: Inflammatory cells within epithelial layer of tubules; mild (1): <25%, moderate (2): 25%- 50%, severe (3): >50% of tubules

Interstitial fibrosis and Tubular atrophy (IFTA): mild (1): <15%, moderate (2): 15%–25%, severe (3): > 25%-50%, very severe (4): >50% of cortical area and tubules [2,3].

Definition of proliferative LN (2003 ISN/RPS classification of lupus nephritis) [7]

Class III: Focal LN

III (A): Purely active lesions: focal proliferative LN.

III (A/C): Active and chronic lesions: focal proliferative and sclerosing LN. III. (C): Chronic inactive lesions with Glomerular scars: focal sclerosing LN.

Class IV: Diffuse LN

IV-S (A) or IV-G (A): Purely active lesions: diffuse segmental (S) or global (G) proliferative LN. IV-S (A/C) or IV-G (A/C): Active and chronic lesions: diffuse segmental or global proliferative and sclerosing LN.

IV-S (C) or IV-G (C): Inactive with glomerular scars: diffuse segmental or global sclerosing LN.

S: >50% of affected glomeruli have segmental lesions.

G: >50% of affected glomeruli have global lesion.

Statistical Analysis

Following data collection, the collected data were assessed for completeness, accuracy and consistency before analysis was commenced. Data analysis was carried out by using SPSS version 26 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). The continuous data with normal distribution were expressed as means ± standard deviation (SD) and were analyzed using paired t-test for same group of patients and ANOVA test for different group of patients. Categorical data were expressed as frequencies and percentages and were analyzed using the chi-square test and Fisher’s exact test. Statistical significance was considered when p<0.05.

According to Helsinki Declaration for Medical Research involving Human Subjects 1964, all the patients were informed about the study design, the underlying hypothesis and the right of the participants to withdraw themselves from the research at any time and for any reason whatsoever.

Results

Mean age of the participants was 25.79 ± 7.20 years and 84.1% of them were females. Regarding pathological type of based on ISN/RPS, majority (72.0%) belonged to Class IV. Besides, Interstitial Inflammation (84.1%) followed by Acute Tubular Injury (81.7%) were the most common types of tubule-interstitial injuries. Lastly, wire-loop lesions (67.5%), global sclerosis (54.9%) and segmental sclerosis (45.1%) were the most frequently occurring varieties of glomerular lesion among the study participants. Table 1 highlights the socio-demographic and histological attributes of the respondents.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic and Histological Characteristics of the Participants (n=82)

Characteristics	Frequency/Percentage (n/%)
Age [in years]	
(Mean ± SD)	25.79 ± 7.20
Range (Min, Max)	15, 47
Gender	
Female	69 (84.1)
Male	13 (15.9)
Pathological type (ISN/RPS)	
Class III (A)	14 (17.0)
Class III (A/C)	9 (11.0)
Total (Class III)	23 (28.0)
Class IV (A)	29 (35.4)
Class IV (A/C)	30 (36.6)
Total (Class IV)	59 (72.0)
Tubulo-interstitial injuries	
Interstitial Inflammation (II)	69 (84.1)
Acute Tubular Injury (ATI)	67 (81.7)

Interstitial fibrosis and Tubular Atrophy (IFTA)	61 (74.4)
Glomerular lesions	
Wire-loop lesion	54 (67.5)
Global sclerosis	45 (54.9)
Segmental sclerosis	37 (45.1)
Neutrophil infiltration	29 (35.4)
Cellular crescent	20 (24.4)
Necrotizing lesion	18 (22.5)
Subendothelial thrombus	15 (18.3)
Fibro-cellular crescent	6 (7.3)
Fibrous crescent	2 (2.4)

Note: *SD: Standard deviation; Min: Minimum; Max: Maximum.

In case of patterns of distribution of the injuries, 92.9% Class III (A) and 100.0% Class IV (A/C) had II; whereas

88.9% and 100.0% Class III (A/C) along with 96.7% and 93.3% Class IV (A/C) had ATI and IFTA respectively. Statistically significant association was found for all 3 types of injuries, meaning, II (p=0.001); ATI (p=0.025) and IFTA (p=0.003). In terms of severity, it was clearly evident that, 78.6% Class III (A) and 66.7% Class IV (A/C) had mild form of II; 88.9% Class III (A/C) and 60.0% Class IV (A/C) suffered from mild form of ATI and lastly 64.3% Class III A had no grade of IFTA; whereas 55.6% Class III (A/C) and 37.9% Class IV (A) reported mild form of IFTA; 50.0% and 20.0% of Class IV (A/C) complained moderate and severe form of IFTA respectively. Statistically significant association was demonstrated in case of ATI (p=0.014) and IFTA (0.001). Table 2 depicts the patterns of distribution and severity of the tubulo-interstitial injuries in the patients of proliferative LN.

Table 2: Distribution and Severity of Tubulo-Interstitial Injuries among the Participants (n=82)

Tubulo-interstitial injuries	Class III (A) [n=14] (n/%)	Class III (A/C) [n=9] (n/%)	Class IV (A) [n=29] (n/%)	Class IV (A/C) [n=30] (n/%)	p value
Distribution of the Tubulo-interstitial injuries in proliferative lupus nephritis					
II					
Present	13 (92.9)	5 (55.5)	21 (72.4)	30 (100.0)	0.001 ^s
Absent	1 (7.1)	2 (44.4)	8 (27.6)	0 (0.0)	
ATI					
Present	9 (64.2)	8 (88.9)	21 (72.4)	29 (96.7)	0.025 ^s
Absent	5 (35.7)	1 (11.1)	8 (27.6)	1 (3.3)	
IFTA					
Present	5 (35.7)	9 (100.0)	19 (65.5)	28 (93.3)	0.003 ^s
Absent	9 (64.3)	0 (0.0)	10 (34.5)	2 (6.7)	
Severity of the Tubulo-interstitial injuries in proliferative lupus nephritis					
II					
Absent	1 (7.1)	4 (44.4)	8 (27.6)	0 (0.0)	0.008
Mild	11 (78.6)	3 (33.3)	12 (41.4)	20 (66.7)	
Moderate	2 (14.3)	2 (22.2)	9 (31.0)	10 (33.3)	
ATI					
Absent	5 (35.7)	1 (11.1)	8 (27.6)	1 (3.3)	0.014 ^s
Mild	8 (57.1)	8 (88.9)	13 (44.8)	18 (60.0)	
Moderate	1 (7.1)	0 (0.0)	8 (27.6)	11 (36.7)	
IFTA					
Absent	9 (64.3)	0 (0.0)	10 (34.5)	2 (6.7)	0.001 ^s
Mild	3 (21.4)	5 (55.6)	11 (37.9)	7 (23.3)	
Moderate	2 (14.3)	4 (44.4)	8 (27.6)	15 (50.0)	
Severe	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	6 (20.0)	

Note: *p value estimated by Fisher’s exact test; s: statistically significant; II: Interstitial Inflammation; ATI: Acute Tubular Injury; IFTA: Interstitial Fibrosis and Tubular Atrophy.

Regarding Interstitial Inflammation, statistically significant association was discerned in case of global sclerosis (p=0.001); neutrophil infiltration (p=0.026); cellular crescent (p=0.039); necrotizing lesion (p=0.013) and subendothelial thrombus (p=0.027). Coming to acute tubular injury, wire-loop lesion (p=0.029) and

cellular crescent (p=0.041) displayed statistically significant association. Lastly, pointing towards IFTA, it was revealed that, wire-loop lesion (p=0.012); global sclerosis (p=0.001) and fibrous crescent (p=0.001) were the types of glomerular lesions where statistically significant association was seen. Table 3 compares the

demographic and histological attributes of II, ATI and IFTA.

It is quite evident that, statistically significant association was detected between Group A & B (p=0.046); A & C (p=0.017); A & D (p=0.001) and B & D (p=0.014) in case of baseline serum creatinine.

Whereas, in terms of serum creatinine after 6 months, Group A & C (p=0.004); A & D (0.001); B & D (p=0.001) and C & D (p=0.003) revealed statistically significant association. Table 4 illustrates the statistical significance of serum creatinine levels based on severities of II, ITA and IFTA.

Table 3: Comparisons of Demographic and Histological Parameters with the Severities of II, ATI and IFTA (n=82)

Characteristics	Absent	Mild	Moderate	Severe	p value
II	(n=13)	(n=46)	(n=23)	(n=0)	
Age (Mean ± SD) [in years]	26.23 ± 6.89	25.83 ± 8.45	25.61 ± 6.83	-	0.974
Gender					
Female	10 (76.9)	37 (80.4)	22 (95.7)	-	0.195
Male	3 (23.1)	9 (19.6)	1 (4.3)	-	
Glomerular lesions					
Wire-loop lesions	8 (61.5)	27 (61.4)	19 (82.6)	-	0.133
Global sclerosis	2 (15.4)	21 (45.7)	22 (97.5)	-	0.001 ^s
Segmental sclerosis	5 (38.5)	20 (43.5)	12 (52.2)	-	0.689
Neutrophil infiltration	2 (15.4)	22 (47.8)	5 (21.7)	-	0.026 ^s
Cellular crescent	6 (46.2)	12 (26.1)	2 (8.7)	-	0.039 ^s
Necrotizing lesion	2 (15.4)	6 (13.1)	10 (43.5)	-	0.013 ^s
Subendothelial thrombus	3 (23.1)	4 (8.7)	8 (34.8)	-	0.027 ^s
Fibro-cellular crescent	1 (7.7)	4 (8.7)	1 (4.3)	-	0.806
Fibrous crescent	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (8.7)	-	0.072
ATI	(n=15)	(n=47)	(n=20)	(n=0)	-
Age (Mean ± SD) [in years]	25.33 ± 10.97	25.89 ± 6.81	26.05 ± 7.22	-	0.914
Gender					
Female	12 (80.0)	42 (89.4)	15 (75.0)	-	0.301
Male	3 (20.0)	5 (10.6)	5 (25.0)	-	
Glomerular lesions					
Wire-loop lesion	8 (53.3)	28 (62.2)	18 (90.0)	-	0.029 ^s
Global sclerosis	7 (46.6)	26 (55.4)	12 (60.0)	-	0.732
Segmental sclerosis	4 (26.7)	24 (51.1)	9 (45.0)	-	0.254
Neutrophil infiltration	6 (40.0)	18 (38.3)	5 (25.0)	-	0.533
Cellular crescent	6 (40.0)	13 (27.7)	1 (5.0)	-	0.041 ^s
Necrotizing lesion	3 (20.0)	12 (26.7)	3 (15.0)	-	0.622
Subendothelial thrombus	2 (13.3)	9 (19.1)	4 (20.0)	-	0.856
Fibro-cellular crescent	0 (0.0)	6 (12.8)	0 (0.0)	-	0.089
Fibrous crescent	1 (6.7)	0 (0.0)	1 (5.0)	-	0.241
IFTA	(n=21)	(n=26)	(n=29)	(n=6)	
Age (Mean ± SD) [in years]	24.1 ± 7.33	27.65 ± 9.03	25.21 ± 5.8	27.0 ± 10.84	0.424
Gender					
Female	18 (85.7)	22 (84.6)	23 (79.3)	6 (100.0)	0.641
Male	3 (14.3)	4 (15.4)	6 (20.7)	0 (0.0)	
Glomerular lesions					
Wire-loop lesion	10 (47.6)	14 (53.8)	25 (86.2)	5 (83.3)	0.012 ^s

Global sclerosis	6 (28.6)	7 (26.9)	26 (89.7)	6 (100.0)	0.001 ^s
Segmental sclerosis	2 (9.5)	12 (46.2)	17 (58.6)	6 (100.0)	0.001
Neutrophil infiltration	9 (42.9)	9 (34.6)	11 (37.9)	0 (0.0)	0.273
Cellular crescent	8 (38.1)	4 (15.4)	8 (27.6)	0 (0.0)	0.146
Necrotizing lesion	4 (21.1)	5 (19.2)	9 (31.0)	0 (0.0)	0.347
Subendothelial thrombus	0 (0.0)	8 (30.8)	5 (17.2)	2 (33.3)	0.087
Fibro-cellular crescent	0 (0.0)	2 (7.7)	4 (13.8)	0 (0.0)	0.297
Fibrous crescent	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (33.3)	0.001 ^s

Note: *p value for age category determined by ANOVA test; p value for gender and glomerular lesions category estimated by Fisher’s Exact Test; SD: standard deviation; II: Interstitial Inflammation; ATI: Acute Tubular Injury; IFTA: Interstitial Fibrosis and Tubular Atrophy.

Table 4: Level of Significance of Serum Creatinine after 6 Months of Induction Therapy Based on Severities of II, ATI and IFTA (n=82)

Groups		Level of significance	
		Serum creatinine (after 6 months)	
II			
Group A	Group B	0.344	
Group A	Group C	0.025 ^s	
Group B	Group C	0.020 ^s	
ATI			
Group A	Group B	0.302	
Group A	Group C	0.027 ^s	
Group B	Group C	0.024 ^s	
IFTA		Baseline Creatinine	S. Creatinine after 6 months
Group A	Group B	0.046 ^s	0.275
Group A	Group C	0.017 ^s	0.004 ^s
Group A	Group D	0.001 ^s	0.001 ^s
Group B	Group C	0.534	0.098
Group B	Group D	0.014 ^s	0.001 ^s
Group C	Group D	0.069	0.003 ^s

Note: *Group A: Absent; Group B: Mild; Group C: Moderate; Group D: Severe; s: statistically significant; II: Interstitial Inflammation; ATI: Acute Tubular Injury; IFTA: Interstitial Fibrosis and Tubular Atrophy; ANOVA test followed by post-Hoc test (bonferroni) was done to measure the level at significance between the groups.

It was observed that, almost two-third (64.5%) patients with mild II revealed complete response. About half (51.6%) patients of mild ATI had complete response. In addition, nearly half (48.4%) patients of mild IFTA reported complete response. The differences of interstitial inflammation (p=0.001) and IFTA (p=0.001)

were statistically significant; however, acute tubular injury was not statistically significant (p=0.106) among three groups. Table 5 elaborates the association of tubulo-interstitial injuries and post-induction therapy response in the study subjects of proliferative LN.

Table 5: Association of Tubulo-Interstitial Injuries and Post-Induction Therapy Response in Proliferative LN (n=82)

Tubulo-interstitial inflammation	Complete response (n=31; %=38.0) [n/%]	Partial response (n=26; %=31.5) [n/%]	Deterioration (n=25; 30.5%) [n/%]	p-value
II				
Absent	6 (19.4)	7 (26.9)	0 (0.0)	0.001 ^s
Mild	20 (64.5)	17 (65.4)	9 (36.0)	
Moderate	5 (16.1)	2 (7.7)	16 (64.0)	
ATI				

Absent	7 (22.6)	7 (26.9)	1 (4.0)	0.106
Mild	16 (51.6)	17 (65.4)	14 (56.0)	
Moderate	5 (16.1)	5 (19.2)	10 (40.0)	
IFTA				
Absent	11 (35.5)	6 (23.1)	4 (16.0)	0.001 ^s
Mild	15 (48.4)	10 (38.5)	1 (4.0)	
Moderate	5 (16.1)	10 (38.5)	14 (56.0)	
Severe	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	6 (24.0)	

s: statistically significant; p-value obtained from Fisher’s exact test.; II: Interstitial inflammation; ATI: Acute Tubular Injury; IFTA: Interstitial Fibrosis and Tubular Atrophy.

Discussion

This prospective, observational, multicenter study was performed to assess the frequency and severity of tubulointerstitial (TI) injuries in proliferative LN and to determine the association of TI injuries with the response after induction therapy.

In this study, the mean age of the study population was 25.79 ± 7.20 years. Baqui et al. found similar mean age (26 ± 11.97) years of SLE with renal involvement in a previous study [12]. Besides, among the participants, females were more predominant with male-to-female ratio of 1:5.3. Although the pathogenesis of SLE remains incompletely understood; it is apparently more frequently encountered in females. Another study has shown a male-to-female ratio of 1:6 in LN in Bangladeshi SLE patients which is congruent to our findings [13].

The frequency of each TI injury was over 74% among the study population. Additionally, Pagni and mates reported that, TI injuries are common in proliferative LN especially class IV than non-proliferative LN [14]. In this study, the most commonly detected TI injury was interstitial inflammation (84%). It was also more frequent in class IV LN and was present in all the patients with class IV (A/C). Acute tubular injury (81.7%), was the second most common TI injury and IFTA was seen in 74.4% of patients. The acute tubular injury and IFTA were more common in class III (A/C) and class IV (A/C). The presence of different TI injuries was significant among all the classes of proliferative LN. Our findings are consistent with previous studies [15,16].

The current study demonstrated that, mild interstitial inflammation was common in class III (A) compared to the other sub-classes; moderate interstitial inflammation in both class IV (A/C) and class IV (A) than class III. Although, mild acute tubular injury was observed among all the sub-classes; however, moderate acute tubular injury was more frequent in both class IV (A/C) and class IV (A) LN than class III. Meanwhile, moderate IFTA was present in patients with both active and chronic lesions than in those with pure active lesions in class III and class IV LN; severe IFTA was found in all class IV (A/C) LN. The severity of interstitial inflammation, acute tubular injury and IFTA were statistically significant (P<0.05) among these four

sub-classes of LN. These findings were in alignment with other studies [15,17].

The current study also found that the glomerular lesions and TI injuries were often present together in most of the patients, but not in all of them, as Lan-ting et al. have also revealed in their study [16]. Therefore, as suggested by Rijnink et al. the ISN/RPS classification could also reflect TI injuries based on the glomerular lesions; however, the ISN/RPS classification focuses on the glomerular lesions only and the TI injuries and other lesions currently obscured in the classification could also be helpful for determining the prognosis of those patients [18].

Assessing the response to treatment after induction therapy, it was observed that complete response (CR) was achieved in 38% of patients. The partial response (PR) was 31.50% and 30.50% of patients had deterioration i.e., treatment failure. The similar renal response was detected in another study done by Mullah et al. [19] In some studies, even though the rate of CR was 14% which was very low [20] the proportion of PR was showed to be quite high at 55% [21]. Causes of proportionately lower CR and higher PR rates in their studies may be due to marked variability of definition of a CR and length of follow-up, ethnic diversity, different induction agents, different drug dose and sample size. In the present study, it was demonstrated that the rate of treatment failure to induction therapy was significantly higher in patients with moderate interstitial inflammation and moderate to severe IFTA. This is in alignment the previous studies [16,18]. It is suggested that proliferative LN patients with II should receive more aggressive treatment to achieve better renal responses. Therefore, it is revealed that, one prognostically important process in proliferative LN is II and active II was the only inflammatory and potentially reversible factor of poor renal responses identified in this study.

Kidney biopsy can be declared as the cornerstone for the diagnosis, categorization and management of lupus nephritis (LN), since the diagnostic and prognostic values of histological features cannot be accurately predicted by any clinical or laboratory test. However, kidney biopsy is an invasive procedure. Even when performed percutaneously under ultrasound guidance,

there are chances of hemorrhagic complication. In a systematic review consisting 118,604 percutaneous kidney biopsies, the most frequent complication was bleeding related to a perirenal hematoma (11%), followed by macroscopic hematuria (3.5%) with needs of erythrocyte transfusion (1.6%) and/or intervention to control bleeding (0.3%), nephrectomy (0.01%), and death (0.06%) [22]. Hence, the benefits of histological evaluation should always be balanced against the bleeding risk in selected patients such as those receiving anticoagulation or those with anti-phospholipid antibodies [23].

Furthermore, the updated criteria enable the earlier classification of lupus nephritis based on kidney biopsy and compatible serology. Treatment of active nephritis consists of low-dose intravenous cyclophosphamide or mycophenolate, followed by maintenance immunosuppression. Moreover, recent trials have highlighted the superiority of regimens combining mycophenolate with either calcineurin inhibitor or belimumab, although their long-term benefit/risk ratio has not been evaluated. In addition, favorable outcomes with novel anti-CD20 antibodies enhance the effectiveness of B cell depletion. Moreover, repeat kidney biopsy can guide the duration of maintenance immunosuppression. LN has raised cardiovascular disease burden calling out for risk-reduction strategies [24].

Like all other studies, this study also had some limitations. First, it was an observational study and sampling technique was purposive. Second, the sample size was relatively small and study duration was short. Third, a number of lesions such as double track sign, arteriosclerosis, interstitial edema, tubular degeneration and cast etc. were not included in this study. Fourth, the biopsy samples were not analyzed to identify the TI injuries by immune-fluorescence or immunohistochemistry and electron microscopy. Fifth, repeat kidney biopsy was not done to see post-induction therapy response. Lastly, the use of NSAIDs was not also controlled, as it is a prevalent factor and can induce interstitial nephritis.

We would suggest that, specific severity of TI injuries should be detected early in patients with LN by light microscopy along with immune-fluorescence or immunohistochemistry and other novel approaches such as functional MRI, novel biomarkers, cell distance mapping etc. Additionally, TI injuries should be one of the targets of treatment for patients with LN especially proliferative LN. Hence, it should be evaluated in future studies such as large randomized controlled trials (RCTs). Furthermore, it is rational that TI injuries should be integrated into the ISN/RPS histological classification of LN.

Conclusion

The acute and chronic TI injuries are quite common in proliferative LN. More severe TI injuries are present in both active and chronic class III and class IV LN than pure active class III and class IV LN. As interstitial inflammation is potentially reversible, the presence of moderately severe interstitial inflammation may identify high-risk patients who would benefit from directed therapeutic interventions. Interstitial inflammation and IFTA may be associated with poor response to induction therapy. Hence, TI injuries should precisely be assessed and treated properly in proliferative LN.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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